

Unsympathetic Aesthetics in Ishiguro's 'Never Let me Go': A Brief Study

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Abstract:

The theme of human identity is a prominent aspect of Kazuo Ishiguro's novel Never Let Me Go, wherein a fictional version of twentieth-century England is depicted, where clone communities exist to serve as a source of organs for transplantation. The novel, similar to Aldous Huxley's Brave New World (1932) and George Orwell's 1984 (1949), presents a dystopian society in which clones grapple with the understanding of their limited individuality. The exploration of the concept of humanity is not unexpected, as it arises from a critical examination of aesthetic and empathetic assumptions influenced by Romanticism. The novel garners attention due to its exploration of genetic engineering, although its underlying concerns can be seen as primarily centred around the ethical implications of artistic creation and consumption within a context of multiculturalism and globalisation. Never Let Me Go, despite its science fiction elements, presents an allegorical narrative that addresses both domestic anxieties regarding the condition of England and international apprehensions surrounding the escalating global disparity. The present study throws light on inhumanity that keeps individuals unaware of their own it masks their own mechanical condition and serves to prepare them for lives of exploitation

Keywords: globalization, inhumane, philosophy, North East Literature and empathy

Introduction

Contrary to expectations, Ishiguro's critique does not relinquish the ethical capacity inherent in artistic creations. On the contrary, this argument presents a compelling perspective on ethics that proposes an alternative approach to art and empathy, emphasising the acknowledgment of the non-human. In contrast to humanist methods of portrayal, Ishiguro's non-humanistic style implies that by acknowledging the mechanical, artificial, and duplicated aspects within ourselves, which are not entirely human in the conventional sense, we can avoid the atrocities committed in the pursuit of safeguarding exclusively human existence. The novel Never Let

Me Go suggests that establishing a sympathetic connection with Ishiguro's protagonists does not rely on the comforting liberal realisation that clones possess human qualities akin to our own. The evolution of art and its associated empathy necessitates a departure from the conventional understanding of the human condition, leading to a deeper recognition of its darker aspects. The story presents a seemingly paradoxical concept: a sympathetic yet inhuman aesthetic that encompasses the mechanical, commodified, and duplicated aspects of individuality.

Although the term "inhuman" is commonly employed to denote acts of cruelty or unethical behaviour, Ishiguro's work presents a contrasting perspective. *Never Let Me Go* redefines empathy for a post humanist era by utilising its aesthetics of replication, enabling individuals to connect with others without relying on restrictive ideas.

The intertwined relationship of Empathy, art and human

The process of empathising with another individual's perspective is intricately linked to our conventional comprehension of human existence. Previous philosophical traditions have assumed that individuals are essentially independent and solely motivated by their own self-interest. However, this perspective overlooks significant aspects of typical human conduct. Richard Rorty asserts that a significant portion of Western moral philosophy focuses on the relatively uncommon archetype of the psychopath, a being devoid of empathy or consideration for others (Rorty, 123). In contemporary psychological discourse, empathy holds a prominent position in both social and biological frameworks that explain the progression of human development. The term empathy was introduced into the English language as a translation of the German aesthetic phrase *einfühlung*. Its incorporation into English occurred in 1909, facilitated by the efforts of E. B. Titchener, an American psychologist (Wispé 78). The user's text is already academic. Titchener employed the term to delineate a physiological phenomenon wherein newborns, aged from birth to ten months, commence imitating the nonverbal gestures and attitudes of others in their immediate environment (Omdahl 25). Referred to as motor mimicry, this nonverbal physiological mechanism was recognised as a manifestation of the instinctual and physiological underpinnings of shared emotions. The user's text is too short to be rewritten academically. During the 1980s, Martin Hoffman, a prominent developmental psychologist from the United States, conducted research that demonstrated the correlation between infants' mechanical mimicry and the subsequent development of advanced cognitive empathy, particularly when children were aware of their distinct individuality from others.

According to Goleman (105), Hoffman's contention was that the acquisition of empathy played a crucial role in facilitating people's ability to make moral evaluations and engage in moral behaviours.

Prior to the advent of contemporary developmental psychology, the concept of empathy (or its equivalent term, sympathy) held a prominent position in theories pertaining to literature and ethics. While several philosophers emphasise the technical distinctions between sympathy and empathy, I employ both terms interchangeably to refer to the cognitive and affective process of connecting with and understanding the experiences of others. The emergence of these beliefs may be traced back to the eighteenth-century philosophical discourse, exemplified by Adam Smith's *Theory of Moral Sentiments* (1759). However, it was in the works of the British Romantics that these views gained heightened prominence and intensity. William Hazlitt contended that a strong and well-developed sense of self necessitates the utilisation of imaginative leaps, which are commonly associated with empathising with others. According to Hazlitt, the connection between our present selves and our future selves is less strong than what our intuition suggests. In contrast, the work titled "An Essay on the Principles of Human Action," published in 1805 by the aforementioned individual, posits that our understanding of our own forthcoming events is contingent upon employing a similar form of imaginative projection that aids us in deducing the inner selves of other individuals. Hazlitt's train of thought culminated in his assertion that this cognitive ability is intrinsically connected to moral conduct: "I would be incapable of loving myself if I did not possess the capacity to love others" (3). The ethical principles of empathic imaginative projection were deeply ingrained in the aesthetic manifestos of William Wordsworth and Percy Bysshe Shelley. Wordsworth, in his *Preface to Lyrical Ballads*, asserts that despite variations in soil, climate, language, manners, laws, customs, and the fading of certain elements from memory or their forceful eradication, the poet unifies the extensive realm of human society across the entire globe and throughout history through the combination of passion and knowledge (259). Shelley, in the same language, asserted that an individual, in order to exhibit great moral virtue, must engage in profound and extensive imagination. This entails empathetically placing oneself in the perspectives of others, encompassing a multitude of individuals. By doing so, one is able to internalise the joys and sorrows experienced by their fellow human beings, making them personally significant. According to the author, the imagination serves as a powerful tool for promoting moral goodness. In this context, poetry plays a crucial role by influencing the

underlying factors that contribute to this effect. The Romantic notions mentioned above were further expanded upon in Victorian literature, wherein the concept of compassion gained significant prominence. As Hina Nazar aptly states, sympathy became a highly regarded ethical term in numerous novels of the nineteenth century (293). George Eliot, the novelist who is often closely linked with ideologies centred around compassionate identification, viewed this concept as a representation of the potential for sorrow and suffering to be transformed into a redemptive state. In his renowned work *Adam Bede*, the author eloquently characterises sympathy as "the singular impoverished term that encompasses our most profound understanding and affection" (488). The enduring influence of Romantic and Victorian ideologies regarding the ethical significance of literary empathy remains evident in the manner in which numerous writers perceive their purpose within contemporary society. However, there have been criticisms against these acknowledgments of the moral, communal, and even governmental possibilities of art that evokes empathy. In the novel "The Portrait of a Lady" (1881) by Henry James, the relationship between the terms "portrait" and "lady" is explored, highlighting the complex and ominous connection that emerges between aesthetics and individual identity. The story implies that Isabel Archer's energy diminishes when subjected to her husband's discerning scrutiny, indicating that observing a piece of art may hinder rather than foster a compassionate connection with the experiences of others. The work also raises the question of whether its own participation in objectification is evident, prompting us to consider whether James's refined prose also plays a role in Isabel's downfall. In a similar vein, E. M. Forster's novel *A Room with a View* satirises the moral insensitivity of the aesthete. This is evident when the character Lucy Honeychurch expresses her dissatisfaction with her fiancé Cecil, stating, "You were perfectly acceptable as long as you confined yourself to inanimate objects, but when it came to dealing with individuals—" (199). The implicit and perhaps inexpressible inference drawn from Lucy's accusation mirrors the moral void that lies at the core of Cecil's tendency to aestheticize. In a more profound manner than the works of James and Forster, who, in their respective approaches, aimed to restore the significance of the human element in art, there existed a contrasting strand of modernist literature that endeavoured to repudiate the assertions of psychological fiction and its extravagant exaltation of the intricacies of ordinary consciousness. In her scholarly investigation of modernist antihumanism, Ella Zohar Ophir demonstrates that authors such as Wyndham Lewis and Laura Riding crafted narratives characterised by their merciless nature, which served as a means to convey scathing

assessments of the importance of commonplace human existence (111). According to these writers, the majority of humanity is perceived as lacking complete humanity. Given the modernists' inclination to separate the independent minority from the mechanised majority (100), they harboured a sense of scepticism towards the potential of empathy. This scepticism stems from the concern that empathy may potentially undermine the distinction between the resilience of individual selfhood and the influence of the collective mass. The authors frequently utilised the anaesthetic qualities of humour and abstraction in order to maintain a distanced and unsympathetic perspective on the unfortunate characters depicted in their literary works. Various writers, such as James, Forster, Lewis, and Riding, each endeavoured to scrutinise the utopian correlation between art, empathy, and human ethical advancement that they had received from the Romantics, albeit in distinct manners. The thematic elements present in the setting of *Never Let Me Go* have a profound resonance with the historical legacy of modern authoritarian repression that characterised the twentieth century. The novel's portrayal of a controlled and mechanised concept of individuality brings to mind Giorgio Agamben's concept of *homo sacer*, which refers to an individual whose very existence is reduced to a mere state of basic life devoid of any rights, as they can be killed by anyone without it being considered a crime (183). Similar to the concept of *homo sacer*, Ishiguro's students possess the ability to be subjected to death, although their demise through the extraction of organs does not serve as a means to attain any form of profound significance, neither for themselves nor for their collective society.

Agamben discerns a fundamental point of reference for the concept of "bare life" in the contemporary concentration camp, a space characterised by its paradoxical nature as it is incorporated into the realm of political existence solely through its complete exclusion. Similar to the literary works *A Pale View of Hills* (1982), *An Artist of the Floating World* (1986), *The Remains of the Day* (1989), and *When We Were Orphans* (2000), *Never Let Me Go* can be interpreted as a contemplation of a society influenced by the eugenic delusions prevalent during Nazi-era confinement. Hailsham, the institution in Ishiguro's narrative, serves as a metaphorical representation of an English boarding school. It effectively establishes a clandestine space that exists outside the scope of permissible political discourse, allowing the characters to develop and flourish within its confines. This particular spatial environment deprives its residents of their entitlement to all types of political identification. Stripped of their citizenship and cultural affiliations, these individuals embody a way of existence that poses a challenge to conventional

understandings of human nature. The portrayal of the concentrationary cosmos in the novel serves as a poignant reminder that art produced in the late twentieth century, following the Holocaust, has sparked profound concerns regarding the feasibility and desirability of empathy. The victims of the Holocaust endured indescribable anguish and erasure. Depictions of their pain, especially when created by someone who did not directly experience it, are often regarded as instances of dehumanising pornography. The experiences of aesthetic pleasure and sympathetic identification seem to contradict each other, so challenging the notion of human solidarity in the face of extreme acts of violence. The user's text is too short to be rewritten academically.

In the period following the Holocaust, there has been a questioning and examination of both the moral principles and the effectiveness of empathy. The emergence of terms such as "compassion fatigue" in the latter part of the twentieth century reflects the inadequacy of representation in motivating individuals to take action on behalf of others. According to Carolyn J. Dean, the aforementioned discourses of numbness have given rise to a novel and introspective narrative concerning the social limitation of moral responsiveness, if not empathy (Dean 5). The scepticism over empathy's ability to humanise establishes the foundation for the fundamental conflict in the novel *Never Let Me Go*. Expanding upon these criticisms, the novel *Never Let Me Go* presents a condemnation of humanist art as it functions to shield the pupils from recognising their inherent lack of humanity, concealing their mechanistic nature, and ultimately conditioning them for lives characterised by exploitation. The act of organ donation serves as a manifestation of Romantic ideals of self-expression, which take on a disconcertingly concrete form. This phenomenon reveals the dystopian implications inherent in the aesthetic of self-expression. Nevertheless, Ishiguro's novel challenges the principles of conventional humanism, yet it does not fully endorse the contempt for automata that is prevalent in certain strands of earlier modernist literature. Furthermore, it does not entirely replicate the subsequent criticisms of pornography or emotional detachment that have arisen in the aftermath of the Holocaust. The story presents a philosophical and artistic perspective on inhuman art as a means to foster a distinct form of empathy towards the raw existence of individuals. This conceptualization proposes a potential means of cultivating empathy towards a mechanised iteration of homo sacer, a type of existence that evades conventional sentiments of compassion.

Dishonesty of Sympathy

Upon initial examination, it may appear unexpected that *Never Let Me Go* would be considered a suitable contender for such an assertion. The novel seemingly reinforces the principles of liberal humanism and liberal humanist empathy through several explicit and implicit means. The user's text is too short to be rewritten in an academic manner. The narrator, Kathy, employs a consistent use of second-person address, establishing her readers as recipients who possess a greater understanding of the intricacies of her world than they actually do. The novel commences with the statement, "I am Kathy H.," as the author introduces herself. I am currently in my thirty-first year of age and have been engaged in the role of a carer for a duration exceeding eleven years. The duration of the task may appear sufficiently lengthy, as acknowledged by the speaker, yet it is imperative to note that an additional period of eight months is expected to be dedicated to its completion (3). The author's use of a self-deprecating tone allows her to establish a connection with her audience as she acknowledges the potential length of her story ("That sounds long enough, I know"). Additionally, she assumes that her readership possesses an understanding of the role of a "carer" and the typical duration of their tenure.

Although the specific circumstances are not yet revealed in the current stage of the work, the readers are positioned as characters who share a common perspective with Kathy. This act of reassurance encourages us to reciprocate the sentiment. The narrator employs many rhetorical strategies throughout her discourse, effectively engaging the readers in the fictional realm of the novel. For instance, she states, "I am uncertain about the circumstances in your location, but at Hailsham, it was mandatory for us to undergo some type of medical procedure nearly every week" (13). The portrayal of liberal empathy in this performance effectively immerses the audience in Kathy's experiences, consistently emphasising the underlying similarities between the narrator and the audience.

Nevertheless, the optimistic portrayal of Kathy's altruistic inclination is undermined by several aspects of her personal narrative, indicating the presence of a more sombre underlying storyline that contrasts with the outward depiction of her role as a carer. What are the specific responsibilities and duties that Kathy is undertaking in her role as a "carer"? She is providing assistance to clones similar to herself, who have been specifically engineered for the purpose of organ donation, in coming to terms with a life characterised by distressing and incapacitating surgical procedures that deprive them of their essential bodily organs. The donors, who are in

their twenties and thirties, will undergo the process of "completion" following their fourth organ donation, avoiding the usage of the term "die". Certain individuals achieve completion at an earlier stage, typically following a limited number of contributions. According to Kathy's account, she is well regarded for her ability to maintain a sense of calm among her patients. She notes that a significant number of her patients have not been categorised as "agitated," even prior to their fourth donation (3). The primary objective of empathy appears to be the reconciliation of patients with their limited existence, characterised by severe affliction and impending mortality.

The lack of resistance exhibited by the cloned pupils has incited significant indignation among readers of Ishiguro's work. They find it perplexing that Kathy and nearly all the other characters in the novel demonstrate no overt resentment towards their circumstances and make limited efforts to challenge their predetermined destiny. Ishiguro elucidates the notion that despite the students' upbringing in sequestered establishments throughout England, they do not endure perpetual detachment from what they perceive as conventional society. During their late adolescence, they reside in a simulated collegiate environment known as "The Cottages," obtain driver's licences, traverse various regions of England, interact with ordinary individuals in commercial establishments and workplaces, and contemplate engaging in intimate relationships with them. However, despite being exposed to firsthand experiences of different lifestyles, the pupils' resistance against their predetermined destiny is remarkably limited. In his review of the novel for the St. Louis Post-Dispatch, Harper Barnes astutely contemplates the hypothetical scenario of an individual facing imminent organ extraction, yet granted temporary freedom to roam the British countryside unrestricted. Barnes suggests that under such circumstances, one might eventually come to the realisation that this arrangement is highly unfavourable, leading them to contemplate relocating to France. With the exception of the student named Tommy, whose unmanageable fits of anger suggest a suppressed anxiety for his destiny, the remaining characters do not appear excessively distressed by their forthcoming experiences of pain and mortality.

Conclusion

Novels similar to those written by Ishiguro do not endorse an aesthetic of detachment, akin to the antihumanist literature that glorifies a relentless separation among individuals. We appreciate Kathy's voice not due to her association with automata, specifically her function as

a "speaking clock," but rather because of her seemingly non-human traits that reflect her existence as a simulacrum. By shedding light on the elements of our personal experiences that fall short of complete human qualities, the act of empathising with Kathy gives rise to a novel aesthetic perspective that fosters empathy in an era characterised by posthumanist ideals. Similar to Ishiguro's other literary works, the absence of certain elements and the presence of underlying themes play a significant role in shaping the narrative. When the novel challenges us to expand our sympathies outside the confines of humanity, it acknowledges the inherent exclusionary and problematic nature of this category. The underlying comparisons drawn between uprooted, genetically-modified pupils and marginalised labourers within a diverse British society and an increasingly interconnected global economy prompt us to acknowledge the substantial number of individuals inside our contemporary reality who are not afforded complete recognition of their humanity.

Similar to the clones, they are relegated to the scarcely discernible realms of serving others, which, in exceptional circumstances, engender Agamben's concept of homo sacer. However, despite the rejection of humanist empathy, it is imperative that we do not relinquish our belief in the capacity of art to evoke empathy.

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